

HOW TO IMPROVE STUDENTS ENGLISH THROUGH MOVIES.

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Annotation: This article provides information that can attract students to have high participation during learning process. Watching English movies can also be used as a technique to improve students' interest. It is not only improving students' interest, but also improving their achievement.

Key words : English Movie, improve English, learning Interest.

So many people would love to learn English through movies, but are not sure how to start. The guide below will help you get the most out of this technique. Movies and films give more than just entertainment. Watching foreign language movies is a fun, motivating way to improve language skills. While enjoying a movie, you can be immersed into authentic and varied language, the visual context and new expressions that you may not find in a textbook. Below Scots gives some ways that watching English movies can help you to learn English, and guide you how to get the most out of this technique. How watching movies helps to improve your English skills

1. Listening skills. Watching movies is a great way to boost your listening skills. You will hear English used in a natural way, informal English, slang words and phrases you do not often find in books or dictionaries.
2. Speaking skills. Repeating what you hear on screen can go a long way towards improving your speaking skills, from your fluency, words linking, pronunciation, to correct intonation.
3. Vocabulary and grammar. You will have chance to learn many words, phrases and grammar and how they are used in real life. Watching movies and films, obviously helps to improve your English. However, while some can use this technique effectively, many people find it difficult, for example, there are no subtitles; they have to keep on pausing and playing to understand; they find it difficult to take notes while enjoying the movie; they are not sure whether they can remember these words after.

So how can learning English through movies be made enjoyable and effective?

1. Enjoy them. You don't need to understand everything. If you try too hard, it will be frustrating experience studying the language. Instead, try catching words and grammar points you already know and those you are not familiar with. You

can pause and replay whenever you find something interesting or if you want to verify something. It is easier and time saving if you have both English subtitles in your mother language. Since not all films have these, you can check the movie transcripts.

2. Re-watching, listening and shadowing. Re-watch your favorite films, and replay your favorite scenes. The more you re-watch, the more you can focus on the speech because you already know what is happening in every scene. Instead of focusing on what is happening, you can give more attention to what you hear. If you don't have time to re-watch the movie, then listen to the film audio. You can rip audios from films, save them as Mp3 files, and play them while doing other things. Also, mimic the way the actors say the lines by repeating them. You can look at the transcripts while doing so.

In a nut shell. Learning English through movies is an enjoyable and effective strategy to improve your language skills. Don't stress yourself too much! Just enjoy watching movies, re-watch, listen and mimic your favorite movies and scenes. The subtitles and transcripts are also a great help. By so doing, you may be amazed at your language improvement as time goes by!

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